

INVESTIGATION INTO THE INFLUENCE OF THE DOUBLE VACUUM BAGGING PROCESS ON CO-CURED SCARF REPAIRS

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of non-monolithic materials such as carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) in aerospace has introduced many new complexities to the materials industry. Historically, the repair of damaged structural aerospace components requires a significant initial financial outlay, highly-skilled operators, and excessive aircraft downtime, leading to the need for repair methods outside the traditional autoclave processes. The application of a double vacuum bagging (DVB) approach for soft patch co-cured scarf lap repairs is demonstrated to offer comparable results to that of a hard patch approach and provides significant benefits over the single vacuum bagging (SVB) method. With the assessment of porosity and tensile strength showing that the DVB method achieved results in-line with the hard patch approach, and that pressure mapping of an uncured sample indicated porosity and premature failure of the specimen, the current study indicates the potential for more consistent repairs of high quality to be achieved using DVB curing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the “never-ending demands for high performance aerospace vehicles with lightweight, highly reliable and durable structures” [1], it is paramount that the materials industry be able to provide novel solutions and sound analytical assessment of this technology. With demands such as sustained supersonic flight, high cruise altitudes, and extreme maneuverability, potential material solutions are continually exposed to more harsh conditions and flight loads. Due to these high-performance demands, in conjunction with the need to reduce financial output and supply wait times, Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) such as CFRPs, will continue to replace conventional aerospace materials such as aluminium alloys (Al-alloys) and titanium alloys (Ti-alloys) [2]. Unlike typical monolithic materials such as aluminum and titanium alloys, the mechanical properties of FRPs are tailorable given fibre orientation and chosen fibre/resin systems. With desirable properties such as high strength-to-weight ratios, corrosion resistance, and ability to produce more complex shapes [3], FRPs will help absorb the current 10-year backlog currently being experienced by aircraft manufacturers [4]. However, high manufacturing and overhead costs dictate the need for reliable, cost-effective repair strategies, in conjunction with sensitivity to manufacturing processes and matrix-reinforcement interaction [5].

These shortcomings, which were formerly addressed for autoclave manufacturing processes, are now being re-experienced with the current industry demand for Out-of-Autoclave (OOA) repair systems for aircraft. The use of bonded scarf repairs, which display the greatest joint efficiency of any repair type and can restore up to 80% of the parent strength [6]. For decreased costs and equipment requirements, the application of a co-cured soft patch, where uncured prepregs plies are cut to match the parent scarf and cured simultaneously with the adhesive, have seen significant research. Unlike a hard mould approach where a panel is cured then machined to fit the scarf geometry, the soft patch approach removes the need for two cures and machining equipment.

The issues faced with a soft patch approach include limiting the effects of temperature and moisture on the development of porosity while still achieving a high strength component. The presence of porosity can be caused by an array of issues, such as dissolved moisture, presence of

volatiles, or the entrapment of air, with environmental control and correct handling processes required to limit the presence of external porosity causations [7]. The reduction of porosity is also assisted by the use of a DVB method, which assists in the evacuation of air by removing the compaction during the b-stage cure via an outer vacuum bag, which is released during the final cure to place the patch under high relative pressure.

There are currently various papers investigating the effects of DVD on composite production, including papers on DVD scarf repairs [8], however, these utilise a prior b-stage cure away from the parent material, neglecting any potential effect the DVB system may introduce with the presence of the adhesive. This experimental paper studies the effect of the DVB system on a single stage co-cured scarf repair, through assessment of the quality and mechanical performance of the repair. This will be assessed against a hard patch repair and SVB repair, with a pressure mapping system to assess the pressure distribution behavior for the DVB repair.

2 EXPERIMENT METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials and Manufacturing

The laminates studied were manufactured from Cycom 5320-1 T65035 12K 8HS, a carbon/epoxy 8-harness woven satin woven mat, with 35% resin by weight. This is an OOA purpose designed prepreg system for primary and secondary aircraft structures, and as such, ideal for this investigation. A thirty ply layup [(45/0/0/-45/90)]_{3,s} was used for all parent and repair specimens, resulting in theoretical laminate thicknesses of 3.9mm. The adhesive film used for the repairs was a Cytec FM300-2K film, with nominal properties of 489gsm, 0.41mm thickness, with a knitted carrier. This system is designed for co-cured and OOA bonding.

All parent laminates were cured using a DVB method, with the hard patch repair and two additional co-cure repairs conducted using the SVB method. The cure cycle for the co-cured repairs utilised a 1.7°C/minute ramp rate from ambient to 60°C, with a 30minute soak for the DVB, followed by a final ramp to 120°C with a 180minute soak. For the DVB repair, the outer vacuum was released after the 60°C soak, with the final cure conducted under SVB conditions.

2.2 Laminate Machining and Repair Design

To ensure consistency, all specimens were initially laid up as large panels, before being scarfed at 3° using milling. These scarfed surfaces then had additional surface preparation conducted, as advised by the Defence Science and Technology Group. The manufacturing technique used didn't employ a caul plate, with the release film observed to induce surface roughness, which introduced some scarf face deformations, which the implications of will be discussed further along. The general shape of the scarf, for both co-cured and hard patches with the presence of the adhesive is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: General scarf design.

The scarf repairs were cured as larger panels for ease of manufacturing, and to minimise excess

resin bleed out [8], before being cut using a table saw into 25.4mm wide specimens for tensile testing. This also ensures that the specimens evaluated provide a better evaluation of the overall material properties, and any potential inconsistencies throughout the material

2.2 Porosity and Defect Evaluation

The porosity evaluation utilised within this study is based upon general visual inspection before and after mechanical testing. This was used to evaluate trends such as failure mechanisms related to porosity observed along bond lines, through thickness bondline porosity, and parent material delamination/ply adhesion issues. Although basic in nature, this allows for relationships to be observed between manufacturing procedures and joint strength.

This was used in conjunction with pressure mapping conducted using an LX 205:100.100.10 X-sensor with a pressure measurement calibration accuracy of 0.5%. The intent of this system is to analyse the pressure distribution between throughout the patch, bond, and parent, to identify any potential correlations to failure mechanisms or porosity characterisation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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3.1 Bondline Inspection

Aforementioned, initial porosity and defect evaluation was conducted using basic visual inspection. Before testing, specimens were assessed for large defects, such as bondline porosity or failed ply-ply adhesion. This information was collated to determine failure mechanisms and the root cause of premature failure. Neglecting premature failure which was a result of poor manufacturing or pre-existing material defects, such as resin dry areas, the failure observed for 3 of the 4 groups occurred in the same manner along the bond surface, with a combination of interlaminar, intralaminar, and cohesive, as observed by Kwak et al. (2019) [9]. These failure mechanisms have been identified below in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Failure mechanisms identified within the scarf.

The intralaminar failure and cohesive failure were the dominant mechanisms observed throughout each group, with intralaminar failure occurring at the junction of the 0° plies (running across width of the specimen) and the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies [9]. The other significant observation noted was the presence of porosity within the adhesive, and its relationship to porosity observed along the void line. As observed in Figure 3, the comparison between hard patch, SVB, and DVB repairs indicates that the manufacturing process significantly influences the repair quality.

Figure 3: Surface porosity for A) DVB, B) SVB, and C) Hard Patch specimens.

The observations made from these inspections are also identified by Chong et al. (2019) [8], with SVB specimens displaying high adhesive and material porosity, while the hard patch and DVD specimens are essentially void free based upon these visual inspections. This can be attributed to the adhesive restricting volatile flow and entrapping gases along the bondline [8].

Further to this, pressure mapping was conducted on two layup configurations, the first the standard design where the scarfs are matched end-to-end, and a second option where the scarf is offset to account for the thickness of the adhesive. Figure 4 shows the variation in pressure distribution for these two options, using the X-sensor system.

Figure 4: Pressure distribution for A) standard join, and B) offset join.

The two areas identified in Figure 4a are the adhesive overlap and the scarf termination, represented by the area of varying pressure (1) and the low-pressure area (2). This suggests that the pressure distribution is not even throughout the panel, which can be associated to the lack of caul plate, as well as the introduction of thickness through the adhesive. The area of low pressure identified by (2) is of interest, as there is an observable bulge approximately the thickness of the adhesive throughout the scarf area, which was noted for the SVB, DVB, as well as associated distortion of the parent-to-parent specimen.

In comparison, the shift of the scarf has a uniform pressure distribution through the adhesive overlap, with the area of low pressure occurring at the scarf-parent gap, and a more uniform pressure distribution throughout the patch. This specimen displayed a smaller and more uniform thickness when compared with the SVB, DVB, and hard patch specimens, however, has a smaller contact area as the scarf is not in complete contact. The removal of the adhesive overlap would in theory distribute the stress throughout the patch better, however, the presence of an overlap ply would induce the same issues.

The area identified as (4) in Figure 4b does however correlate to specimen failure. This area was identified to have high porosity, similar to that of Figure 3b., when mechanical testing was conducted. This pressure difference could suggest the presence of a resin rich or resin dry area, or may indicate the presence of entrapped air or particles. This specimen was noted to failure prematurely when compared with the rest of the panel specimens, suggesting failure may be able to be predicted through the use of pressure mapping.

The affect of the adhesive with the presence of the adhesive is seen in the scarf thickness in Table 1. As expected, the SVB specimen was the thickest while the Offset Adhesive specimen was the thinnest, however, the higher consistency of the SVB specimen is unexpected, as the hard patch approach would be expected to provide the most consistent thickness due to the lower voidage experienced.

Specimen	Parent-to-Parent	SVB	DVB	DVB- Adhesive	Offset
Thickness (mm)	4.618 ± 0.116	4.763 ± 0.092	4.606 ± 0.147	4.273 ± 0.111	

Table 1. Scarf thickness of the four groups.

This data supports the results observed in Figure 4 as the low-pressure area around the scarf

termination suggests an abrupt height change, consistent with the bulge observed in the scarf.

3.2 Mechanical Performance

The mechanical assessments conducted were limited to assessing the tensile properties of the lap joint, with the results presented in Table 2. Throughout all tests, premature “creaking” noises were observed [10], however, the load at which these were observed offer no relationship to the failure of the specimens and is more likely an indication of the stress being distributed throughout the bondline. The strengths observed for the four different groups of specimens offer an interesting insight into the effect of the manufacturing process.

Specimen	Parent-to-Parent	SVB	DVB	DVB-Offset Adhesive
Tensile Strength (MPa)	408±28	338±62	405±30	354±25

Table 2. Tensile strength of the four groups.

As expected, the hard patch approach produced the greatest strength at 408±28 MPa, while the SVB approach displayed the lowest strength and a large variation of 338±62. This relates to the porosity observed on the failed bondlines, with the extensive porosity of the SVB resulting in lower strengths and higher variability [8]. The failure observed for parent-to-parent, SVB, and DVB all occurred in the same manner, with catastrophic failure indicative of brittle failure occurring for all [8][10]. The offset adhesive specimens however, failed in a different manner, with many initially failing in an interlaminar manner at the 0° plies which were not matched, before catastrophically failing like the other 3 groups at a higher load. This introduced some predictability to the failure mechanism, with the lowest deviation also being noted, however, this method performed only marginally better than the SVB cured specimens and performed significantly worse than the DVB and hard patch methods.

The consistency of the strength for the offset adhesive specimen also suggest that the more uniform stress distribution in Figure 4b has a relationship to the strength. The specimen which was identified to have the porosity indicated by the pressure difference in 4b also failed prematurely, further suggesting that pressure mapping of the scarf region can potentially identify areas of poor quality and reduced strength.

4 CONCLUSION

Overall, the findings suggest that pressure distribution, ply termination, which induces stress risers [8][10][11], and porosity [8][10], are the most influential factors for the repair strength. While these initial studies only offer a brief insight into the potential application of DVB scarf repairs, this study will be furthered upon with more in-depth pressure mapping and porosity evaluation to determine an optimal approach for future repairs. This will be achieved through additional focus on consistency and reliability of the repairs, through considerations of the effect of caul plates, offset lengths for matching parents and patches, and if pressure mapping provides consistent and insightful information on porosity presence, location, and premature failure.

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